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**"APPLICATION OF G.I.S. TECHNIQUES FOR
SPATIAL ANALYSIS OF AGRICULTURAL LAND USE
EFFICIENCY IN THE SOLAPUR DISTRICT, MAHARASHTRA"**

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ABSTRACT

The term agricultural efficiency is denotes the productivity of a particular unit of land. Agricultural productivity is frequently associated with attitude towards work, thrift, industriousness, aspirations for a higher standard of living, etc. Certain farming communities are remarkably efficient in allocating the factors their disposal towards higher level of farm productivity, which are further strengthened by the physical and socio-economic-organizational location variable. Productivity as defined in economics of agricultural geography means output per unit of input or per unit of area respectively, and the improvement in agricultural productivity is generally the result of a more efficient use of the factors of production, viz., environment, arable land, labour, capital and the like. Agricultural land use efficiency may be defined as the extent to which the net sown area is cropped or resown. The gross cropped area as a percent to the net sown area give a measure of land use efficiency which means the intensity of cropping. The study of agricultural land use efficiency gives the idea about identify the problem region related to agricultural land use efficiency.

The prime objective of the study is to analyses the spatial pattern of agricultural land use efficiency in the Solapur district. Present study is based on the secondary source of data. Secondary data obtained from socio-economic abstract of the Solapur district district in the year of 2011-12. Data is processed and represented with the help of using GIS Software. It indicates that the spatial pattern of agricultural land use efficiency is not uniform in the study region. It is low in where physical environment is unfavorable. On the other hand some part of the district have

witnessed high of agricultural land use efficiency. It is mainly due to favorable physical environment & well developed irrigation facilities. The average agricultural land use efficiency of Solapur district is 104.18.

KEYWORDS : Land use efficiency, resown, regional disparities

INTRODUCTION :

Agriculture is the lifeline which contributes highest percent of income in Indian economy. Agricultural development is one of the vital segments of regional development. There are sectoral,

sectional and spatial dimensions of regional development. For the measurement of special development the role of agricultural development is very important, which is mostly depend on agricultural landuse efficiency. So the study of agricultural efficiency is very important of any region. Measuring the independent control of land, labour and capital on agricultural productivity is extremely difficult because they are complementary rather than isolated aspects. Capital productivity means output per unit of input in monetary values but land labour efficiency ultimately affect capital efficiency. Therefore, the economic interpretation of agricultural efficiency needs methods which can assess the output and input ratio, and the input should include land, labour and capital. The term agricultural efficiency is donates the productivity of a particular unit of land. Agricultural landuse efficiency may be defined as the extent to which the net sown area is cropped or resown. The gross cropped area as a percent to the net sown area give a measure of land use efficiency which means the intensity of cropping pattern. The study of agricultural land use efficiency gives the idea about identify the problem region related to agricultural land use efficiency .In this paper an attempt has been made to analyses the spatial pattern of agricultural land use efficiency in the study region.

OBJECTIVES:

Some specific objectives of the study are as follows-

- 1.To study of spatial pattern of Agricultural Landuse Efficiency in solapur district.
- 2.To analysis the regional disparities in Agricultural Landuse Efficiency in study region.
- 3.To know the factors responsible for regional disparities in Agricultural Landuse Efficiency in study region.

STUDY AREA:

Solapur district has been selected as per study which located in western Maharashtra. The district of Solapur lies entirely in Bhima-Sina main river basin of Maharashtra state. The Solapur district bounded by 17035'N to 18032'N latitudes and 75016'E to 76015'E longitudes. The total geographical area of Solapur district is 14845 sq,kms. divided into eleven tahsils. As per 2011 census the total population accounts 4,31,55,227 roughly equal to the nation of Maldova or the US state of Kentucky. This gives it a ranking of 43rd in India (out of total of 640). The total population accounts for 3.84 percent of the state. Solapur district has dry climate. The daily mean maximum temperature range between 30° C to 35° C and minimum temperature range between 18°C to 21°C. The highest temperature is recorded in the month of May. The average annual rainfall is registered 510 mm. The soil of the district essentially derived from the Deccan trap.

DATABASE AND METHODOLOGY:

Present study is based on the secondary source of data. Secondary data obtained from socio-economic abstract of the Solapur district (2011-12), District Census Handbook & District Gazetteers. Statistical tools like percentage, average etc. have been used in the study. Data is processed and represented with the help of GIS Software. The Index of Agricultural Landuse Efficiency (I.L.E) is calculated by using following formula.

$$ILE = \frac{GCA}{NSA} \times 100$$

Where,

ILE= Index of Agricultural Landuse Efficiency

GCA= Gross Cropped Area

NSA= Net Sown Area

Map No.1

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Spatial Pattern of Agricultural Landuse Efficiency:

Index of agricultural landuse efficiency is calculated for each taluqas of Solapur district using the given formula for the measurement of agricultural land use efficiency, which is shown in the Table No1. The following table indicates that Agricultural Landuse Efficiency in Solapur district. The agricultural land use efficiency is not uniform in the study region. It is well proved that physical environment still plays an important role in the agricultural land use efficiency in the study region, because the area which has favorable environment in this area it is found high. In other hand an area where physical environment is not favorable, in such area agricultural land use efficiency is observed low.

Table No.1
Solapur District
Tahsilwise Agricultural Landuse Efficiency
2011-12

Sr. No.	Tahsil	ILE
1	Karmala	102.51
2	Madha	105.49
3	Barshi	102.99
4	N.Solapur	110.98
5	Mohol	103.60
6	Pandharpur	101.76
7	Malshiras	104.28
8	Sangola	104.63
9	Mangalwedha	105.44
10	S.Solapur	104.31
11	Akkalkot	104.60
	Total District	104.18

Source: Socio- Economic Review and District Statistical Abstract of Solapur District 2011-12

ILE= Index of Agricultural Landuse Efficiency

Map No.2 indicates that North western part, North Eastern part and some middle part of the study region has low agricultural landuse efficiency. It includes Karmala, Barshi and Pandharpur tahasils. In this region physical environment is not favorable, where steep slope, hilly and undulating topography is observed. Broken hill range forming a low table land in Karmala tahsil. The central part of Karmala tahsil form a rough broken ground, highly dissected. The hills themselves rise through a succession of structural levels indicative of the horizontal lava flows and are on the surface covered by a fairly deep layer of red murum or broken trap. Therefore irrigation facilities are not developed too much in this region, which play important role in increasing agricultural land use efficiency of the region. Irrigation does not only help to increase agriculture production but also enables to bring more barren land under wet crops and facilitate for double cropping. High agricultural landuse efficiency is mainly concentrated in eastern part of the study region. In this region high agricultural land use efficiency is found due to black soil, gentle slope, well developed irrigation and agricultural infrastructure. In this region North Solapur is included. But some part of Pandharpur, Mangalwedha and Madha are also founded high Agricultural Landuse efficiency.

Map No.2

CONCLUSION:

- 1.Agricultural Landuse Efficiency is not uniform in the study region, due to unfavorable condition.
- 2.It is low in north western part, north eastern part and some middle part of study region.
- 3.Eastern part and some middle part of study region witnessed high agricultural Landuse efficiency due to high irrigation facility at the edge of Bhima Man basin.
4. Average Landuse efficiency of solapur district is 104.18. In the seven tahsil it is more than district average. In which Malshiras(104.28), South Solapur(104.31), Akkalkot(104.60), Sangola(104.63), Mangalwedha (105.44), Madha(105.49) and North Soalpur(110.98) tahsils are included.
- 5.In four tahsil agricultural landuse efficiency is less than average. In which Pandharpur(101.76), Karmala(102.51), Barshi(102.99) and Mohol(103.60) are included.
6. It is proved that physical environment still plays an important role on agricultural landuse efficiency in the study region.
- 7.It is clear that Agricultural landuse efficiency in north western part and north eastern part cannot develop.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- 1.For the increasing the agricultural land use efficiency, irrigation play important role, therefore effort need to be intensified by Government to increase the irrigation facilities in north western and north eastern region where agricultural landuse efficiency is low.
- 2.There is also more scope for increase cultivation land by bring fallow land.
- 3.In the study region where is unfavourable condition for agriculture, so this region some allied occupation of agriculture, like animal husbandary, agro-tourism etc. should be developed.
- 4.It should be necessary to use the Hybrid Seed for increasing Agricultural Landuse efficiency.

5. The agricultural conference helps to increase the Agricultural landuse efficiency.
6. It will be greater to build the small dam where the slope of land is high to
7. Water can be arrested by constructing small dam and agricultural pond in the steep slope region. It will provide water for agriculture during summer season.

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